

Project no.:

763959

Project acronym:

MegaRoller

Project full title:

**Developing the PTO of the first MW-level
Oscillating Wave Surge Converter**

Collaborative project

H2020-LCE-2017-RES-RIA-TwoStage

Start date of project: 2018-05-01

Duration: 36 Months (3 years)

D1.1

Advanced Wave-Structure Interaction Model – Theory and User Manual

Due Project Month: M06

Due delivery date: 2018-10-31

Actual delivery date: 2018-10-24

Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this deliverable:

Cruz Atcheson Consulting Engineers, Lda.

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon 2020 Program (2014-2020)		
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Deliverable number:	D1.1
Deliverable short title:	Advanced Wave-Structure Interaction Model – Theory and User Manual
Deliverable title:	Advanced Wave-Structure Interaction Model – Theory and User Manual
Work package:	WP1 Interaction with Wave Resource
Lead author:	CAT / Laporte Weywada, Pauline
Author	CAT / Cruz, João
Author	CAT / Scriven, Joshua
Author	AWE / Vuorinen, Matti

Revision Control			
Date	Revision	Author(s)	Comments
2018-10-10	1.0	Laporte Weywada Pauline	Initial Version

Quality Assurance, status of deliverable		
Action	Performed by	Date
Verified (WP leader)	Laporte Weywada Pauline (CAT)	10.10.2018
Verified (Sc Coordinator)	Tuula Mäki (AWE)	12.10.2018
Approved (Coordinator)	Ilpo Honkanen (Hydroll)	24.10.2018

Abstract

This document constitutes a theory and user manual of the MegaRoller wave energy converter (WEC) model developed under WP1 in a custom version of the numerical simulation package WEC-Sim. The present deliverable is the main output of Task 1.2, aiming to define and develop a nonlinear model of the MegaRoller WEC to assess the influence of the distributed loading contributions over the WEC prime mover, i.e. the flap, accounting for the coupled nature of interaction(s) between the flap and the power take-off (PTO) load sources. The outputs of Task 1.2 aim to support the design process to be conducted in WP2.

This document describes the fundamental theory associated with the WEC-Sim model and the essential aspects related to its practical use. In essence, the developed model aims to enable the estimation of hydrodynamic, structural and all relevant mechanical loads for devices that involve rigid bodies, PTO systems and moorings. Simulations are performed in the time-domain by solving the governing WEC equations of motion in all relevant degrees-of-freedom, in a fully-coupled format (i.e. simultaneously accounting for all relevant load sources). WEC models are constructed on a multi-body basis. This approach allows a WEC to be constructed by linking together a number of constituent bodies, representing different physical entities in the machine. Each body must incorporate one or more components, which are used to describe the key WEC characteristics. Multi-body modelling allows a wide range of WEC concepts to be modelled using a consistent, fully-coupled engineering code.

The description of the code functionalities is supported by a preliminary validation exercise, using the previous design iteration of the WaveRoller WEC as tested in the Queen's University of Belfast between August 2017 and January 2018 (see e.g. <http://aw-energy.com/news/awe-and-queens-university-belfast-finish-waveroller-tank-tests/>). The pre-validation exercise showed good comparisons in terms of PTO torque and prime mover motion in pitch, both for regular and irregular waves.

However, it is recognised that development work on the WEC-Sim model of the MegaRoller WEC will continue throughout the course of the MegaRoller project. As a consequence, the theoretical formulation and practical aspects here described are subject to future updates. In particular, it is envisaged that the consideration of a number of further nonlinear effects relevant for large structure such as the MegaRoller WEC will be required, potentially leading to changes in the core formulation and the introduction of novel / updated features. Such nonlinear effects may include the consideration of fluid-structure interactions, or slap and slam loads. Some of these initial features are also introduced in this report, guiding the development of the MegaRoller WEC-Sim model to be conducted in Task 1.3.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document constitutes a theory and user manual of the MegaRoller wave energy converter (WEC) model developed under WP1 in a custom version of the numerical simulation package WEC-Sim. The present deliverable is the main output of Task 1.2, aiming to define and develop a nonlinear model of the MegaRoller WEC to assess the influence of the distributed loading contributions over the WEC prime mover, i.e. the flap, accounting for the coupled nature of interaction(s) between the flap and the power take-off (PTO) load sources. The outputs of Task 1.2 aim to support the design process to be conducted in WP2.

This document describes the fundamental theory associated with the WEC-Sim model and the essential aspects related to its practical use. In essence, the developed model aims to enable the estimation of hydrodynamic, structural and all relevant mechanical loads for devices that involve rigid bodies, PTO systems and moorings. Simulations are performed in the time-domain by solving the governing WEC equations of motion in all relevant degrees-of-freedom, in a fully-coupled format (i.e. simultaneously accounting for all relevant load sources). WEC models are constructed on a multi-body basis. This approach allows a WEC to be constructed by linking together a number of constituent bodies, representing different physical entities in the machine. Each body must incorporate one or more components, which are used to describe the key WEC characteristics. Multi-body modelling allows a wide range of WEC concepts to be modelled using a consistent, fully-coupled engineering code.

The description of the code functionalities is supported by a preliminary validation exercise, using the previous design iteration of the WaveRoller WEC as tested in the Queen's University of Belfast between August 2017 and January 2018 (see e.g. <http://aw-energy.com/news/awe-and-queens-university-belfast-finish-waveroller-tank-tests/>). The pre-validation exercise showed good comparisons in terms of PTO torque and prime mover motion in pitch, both for regular and irregular waves.

However, it is recognised that development work on the WEC-Sim model of the MegaRoller WEC will continue throughout the course of the MegaRoller project. As a consequence, the theoretical formulation and practical aspects here described are subject to future updates. In particular, it is envisaged that the consideration of a number of further nonlinear effects relevant for large structure such as the MegaRoller WEC will be required, potentially leading to changes in the core formulation and the introduction of novel / updated features. Such nonlinear effects may include the consideration of fluid-structure interactions, or slap and slam loads. Some of these initial features are also introduced in this report, guiding the development of the MegaRoller WEC-Sim model to be conducted in Task 1.3.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope of the Document

This document constitutes a theory and user manual of the MegaRoller wave energy converter (WEC) model developed under WP1. The model is developed in a custom version of the numerical simulation package WEC-Sim (see Section 2.1). The primary objective of the model is to enable a detailed assessment of the distributed loads affecting the MegaRoller WEC system, in an effort to support the design process in WP2. The present deliverable is the main output of Task 1.2, which aims to define and develop a nonlinear model of the MegaRoller WEC to assess the influence of the distributed loading contributions over the WEC prime mover, i.e. the flap, accounting for the coupled nature of interaction(s) between the flap and the power take-off (PTO) load sources.

This document describes the fundamental theory associated with the WEC-Sim model and the essential aspects related to its practical use. The description of the code functionalities is supported by a preliminary validation exercise, using the previous design iteration of the WaveRoller WEC as tested in the Queen's University of Belfast between August 2017 and January 2018 (see e.g. <http://aw-energy.com/news/awe-and-queens-university-belfast-finish-waveroller-tank-tests/>). However, it is recognised that development work on the WEC-Sim model of the MegaRoller WEC will continue throughout the course of the MegaRoller project. As a consequence, the theoretical formulation and practical aspects here described are subject to future updates. In particular, it is likely that subsequent verification and validation exercises, focusing on the MegaRoller WEC, will assist the consortium in identifying potential limitations of the current formulation, potentially leading to changes in the core formulation and the introduction of novel / updated features, either during the MegaRoller project or in future work.

Following this introduction (Section 1), an overview of the WEC-Sim numerical simulation package is presented (Section 2). This includes a brief characterisation of each key module, and the linkage between all critical components. Section 3 introduces background information regarding the theoretical formulation, followed by specific details associated with the core modules of WEC-Sim (including, where applicable, suitable modifications to key features). In particular, details regarding the hydrodynamic, structural dynamics and PTO / control modules of WEC-Sim are provided in Sections 3.2 to 3.4, respectively. In Section 4, practical background information on the WEC-Sim code is provided (Section 4.1), followed by aspects associated with the input structure (Sections 4.2 to 4.4), simulation setup (Section 4.5) and output structure (Section 4.6) of the WEC-Sim model. A case study is then presented in Section 5, in the form of a preliminary validation exercise related to the Queen's University of Belfast tests. Finally, this document is concluded in Section 6, where next steps envisaged in the context of the MegaRoller project are proposed.

1.2 Purpose of the Software

WEC-Sim (Wave Energy Converter SIMulator) is an open-source WEC simulation tool, developed in MATLAB/Simulink using the multi-body dynamics solver SimMechanics. The WEC-Sim project is funded by the U.S. Department of Energy's Wind and Water Power Technologies Office, and the code development effort is a collaboration between the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) and Sandia National Laboratories (SNL).

In its original formulation, WEC-Sim has the ability to model WEC devices that involve rigid bodies, PTO systems and moorings. Simulations are performed in the time-domain by solving the governing WEC equations of motion in all relevant degrees-of-freedom, in a fully-coupled format (i.e. simultaneously accounting for all relevant load sources).

The key objective of the WEC-Sim model developed in WP1 is to enable a detailed characterisation of the dominant loading patterns affecting the WEC, to inform the design process (WP2). In particular, the final MegaRoller WEC model aims to assess the effects of the distributed loading contributions over the WEC prime mover, i.e. the flap, on the PTO system. Such effects require the conceptualisation of a novel structural dynamics module, enhancing the load (only) capabilities currently available in WEC-Sim. The influences of a range of nonlinearities (hydrodynamic and mechanic) are also expected to be considered as part of the WEC-Sim model developments (see also Section 2.3).

1.3 Acceptance Criteria

This document fulfils the following milestone objective set out in the Grant Agreement [GA, 2018]:

- *“Simulation code functional and results acceptable based on engineering judgement”*

Additionally, the document also adheres to the description of the deliverable provided in the Grant Agreement [GA, 2018]:

- *“Contain sufficient detail that a new user of the software can implement and use the software. The process is defined in a flow chart or similar and the theory behind the software will be adequately described”*

2 OVERVIEW OF THE SOFTWARE

2.1 Structure of the Software

In its original formulation, WEC-Sim has the ability to model devices that involve rigid bodies, PTO systems and moorings. Simulations are performed in the time-domain by solving the governing WEC equations of motion in all relevant degrees-of-freedom, in a fully-coupled format (i.e. simultaneously accounting for all relevant load sources).

WEC-Sim enables the estimation of hydrodynamic, structural and mechanical loads. A range of PTO systems can be modelled to enable the estimation of power absorption and the impact of all relevant forces on the WEC's response.

WEC models are constructed on a multi-body basis. This approach allows a WEC to be constructed by linking together a number of constituent bodies, representing different physical entities in the machine. Each body must incorporate one or more components, which are used to describe the key WEC characteristics. Multi-body modelling allows a wide range of WEC concepts to be modelled using a consistent, fully-coupled engineering code.

Figure 2.1 provides an overview of the WEC-Sim workflow. The flow chart summarises the main components that are used in the modelling process. A more detailed description of the inputs and outputs to each component of the tool is provided in the subsequent sections of this document, focusing on the theory (see Section 3) and on the practical aspects of the implementation (see Section 4). The arrows in Figure 2.1 denote the flow of data in the software. It is noted that potential changes to the flow of data featured in Figure 2.1 may be required in the context of the proposed model developments (e.g. conceptualisation of a structural dynamics module – see Section 3.3.2).

Figure 2.1 WEC-Sim flow chart (source: <https://wec-sim.github.io/WEC-Sim/overview.html#>)

The primary blocks (defined in WEC-Sim as *classes*) that interact to solve the multi-body dynamics of the WEC include (see also the items below the WEC-Sim input file column in Figure 2.1):

- *Body class*, that defines the body properties (e.g. mass, moment of inertia, centre of gravity, hydrodynamic properties);
- *Wave class*, that defines the wave conditions for the simulation;
- *Constraint class*, to connect the WEC bodies to one another and the seabed with defined degree of freedom (DOFs) constrains;
- *PTO class*, which connects the WEC bodies to one another (and possibly to the seabed) by constraining DOFs and applying linear damping and stiffness.

Finally, the mooring arrangement can be represented using a quasi-static formulation or by using the mooring forces calculated from MoorDyn¹. However, due to the current principles and layout of the MegaRoller WEC, i.e. an Oscillating Wave Surge Converter (OWSC) hinged to a foundation fixed to the seabed, the mooring class is not used and will not be further described in this document.

2.2 A Time-Domain Formulation

In WEC-Sim, simulations are performed in the time-domain by solving the governing WEC equations of motion in all relevant degrees-of-freedom, accounting for all relevant load sources. This allows for the influence of e.g. nonlinear forces and nonlinear structural elements to be considered.

Three different methods to solve the equation of motions are available in WEC-Sim: the sinusoidal steady-state, the convolution integral and the state-space representation method. The sinusoidal steady-state response is primarily suited for simple WEC designs, with regular incoming waves. However, for random sea simulations or any simulations where fluid memory effects of the system are essential, the convolution integral method is recommended to represent the fluid memory (retardation) force. To reduce the computational effort associated with the convolution integral(s), the state space representation method can be used to approximate this calculation as a system of linear ordinary differential equations.

Independently of the method selected to solve the equation of motions, the hydrodynamic forces are calculated using hydrodynamic coefficients obtained via boundary element method (BEM) potential flow solvers (e.g., WAMIT², AQWA³, and NEMOH⁴). The WEC-Sim model(s) described in this document include diffraction, radiation and hydrostatic effects, with the WEC response being largely dominated by reactive, rather than resistive, hydrodynamic forces.

2.3 A Nonlinear Model

The WEC-Sim MegaRoller WEC model is particularly well suited for situations where body motions are of a similar order of magnitude to the water particle kinematics, which in general terms may be associated with moderate, performance related environmental conditions. Additionally, it should be noted that

¹ Matthew Hall. Moordyn user's guide. 2015.

² CH Lee and JN Newman. WAMIT User Manual. 2006.

³ ANSYS Aqwa. URL: <http://www.ansys.com/Products/Other+Products/ANSYS+AQWA>

⁴ Nemoh a Open source BEM. URL: <http://openore.org/tag/nemoh/>

irregular wave simulations are less likely to exhibit pronounced resonance effects than those that may occur in regular waves.

Large body motions, which may occur as a result of e.g. low PTO damping or the excitation of resonant modes, can result in high levels of reported output power. In real scenarios, nonlinearities in the hydrodynamic loading and / or the presence of viscous effects may act to suppress such large motions.

In order to account for such effects, the MegaRoller WEC-Sim model is able to consider a number of nonlinearities, namely (see also Section 3):

- Nonlinear Froude-Krylov hydrodynamics and hydrostatics may be used to account for the nonlinear hydrodynamic forces induced by the instantaneous water surface elevation and body position, where the force components are obtained by integrating the static and dynamic pressures over each panel along the wetted body surface at each time step.
- Added-mass and viscous damping forces can be included by using e.g. Morison -type corrections to account for additional nonlinear force contributions.
- The force components on the hydrodynamic properties can be completed using a database of input hydrodynamic coefficients considering a range of pitch angle positions of the flap, selecting the most appropriate coefficients based on the flap position at the given time step.
- An empirical correction to implement the effects of slap and slam forces in WEC-Sim enables the estimation of the pressure distribution over the body during slam and slap events to be obtained, to improve the fidelity of load estimates on surface piercing bodies in aggressive environmental conditions.
- In order to assess the effects of the distributed loading contributions over a non-rigid flap, a novel structural dynamics module enables the accounting of fluid-structure interaction (FSI) effects across the WEC prime mover.

It is noted that in the preliminary results presented in Section 5, only viscous damping forces and nonlinear Froude-Krylov hydrodynamics and hydrostatics are considered. However, it is likely that the additional nonlinear features will be required for the ongoing development of the WEC-Sim model of the MegaRoller WEC. Verification and validation activities are planned in the context of Task 1.4, to assess the need for potential improvements in simulation accuracy.

3 THEORY

3.1 Background: Linear Wave Theory

In this section, the background hydrodynamic theory relevant to WEC-Sim is presented. At a high-level, the dynamic response of the system is calculated by solving the applicable equation of motion [Babarit, 2012], [Nolte, 2014]. For a generic floating body, the equation of motion is given by:

$$m\ddot{X} = F_{exc}(t) + F_{rad}(t) + F_{PTO}(t) + F_v(t) + F_B(t) + F_m(t) \quad (1)$$

where \ddot{X} is the (translational and rotational) acceleration of the device, m is the mass matrix, F_{exc} is the wave excitation force, F_{rad} the force resulting from wave radiation, F_{PTO} the PTO force, F_v the damping force vector, F_B the net buoyancy restoring force, and F_m the mooring force.

WEC-Sim relies on linear wave theory to estimate various hydrodynamic variables, which are in turn used as inputs to the time-domain equations of motion. The key assumptions on which this theory is based, an overview of the Boundary Element Method (BEM) and of the quantities derived using linear theory and used by WEC-Sim are outlined in this section.

In WEC-Sim, wave forcing components are modelled using linear coefficients obtained from a frequency-domain potential flow BEM solver (e.g. WAMIT², AQWA³, and NEMOH⁴ – see Section 2.2). The BEM solutions are obtained by solving the Laplace equation for the velocity potential, which assumes the flow is inviscid, incompressible, and irrotational.

It is beyond the scope of this document to present a detailed review of linear wave theory; such an exercise can be found in one of the many available references in this field, such as [Le Méhauté, 1976], [Newman, 1977], [Mei, 1989], [Falnes, 2002]. However, it is relevant to briefly summarise the equations that define the boundary value problem, and the main simplifying assumptions that are implemented in a BEM model when solving the wave-structure interaction problem.

The approach performed in first-order BEM solvers is conditioned by the underlying principles of linear wave theory. In particular:

- The free-surface and the body boundary conditions are linearised.
- The fluid is incompressible, and the flow is irrotational (potential flow): $\nabla^2 \Phi = 0$, where Φ is the velocity potential.
- Viscous effects like shear stresses and flow separation are not considered.
- The seabed is assumed to be flat (and uniform).

Once the velocity potential has been estimated, the hydrodynamic coefficients and wave excitation force quantities used as inputs by WEC-Sim can be derived as follows:

- The hydrodynamic coefficients comprise both the added-mass $A_{i,j}$ and the radiation damping $B_{i,j}$ coefficients. These quantities represent the solutions of the radiation problem (i.e. the problem related to the motion of a body in an otherwise undisturbed fluid field). The linear added-mass and damping coefficients are related via:

$$A_{i,j} - \frac{i}{\omega} B_{i,j} = \rho \iint_{S_b} \frac{\partial \phi_i}{\partial n} \phi_j dS \quad (2)$$

where φ_i is the velocity potential associated with the modes of motion, $\frac{\partial \varphi_i}{\partial n}$ the normal derivative of φ_i and S_b is the mean wetted surface.

- The wave exciting force $F_{exc,i}$ can be calculated in two different ways: through the Haskind relation, which links the damping coefficients and the exciting force:

$$F_{exc,i} = -i\rho\omega \iint_{S_b} \left(\varphi_0 \frac{\partial \varphi_i}{\partial n} - \varphi_i \frac{\partial \varphi_0}{\partial n} \right) dS \quad (3)$$

or directly via integration of the hydrodynamic pressure:

$$F_{exc,i} = -i\rho\omega \iint_{S_b} \frac{\partial \varphi_i}{\partial n} \varphi_S dS \quad (4)$$

where, φ_0 is the velocity potential associated with the incident wave, φ_i is the velocity potential associated with the modes of motion and φ_S is the sum of the incident and the diffracted velocity potentials (also referred to as scatter).

Note that in the above, and for body N , the i and j indexes $1*N$ to $6*N$ refer to surge, sway, heave, roll, pitch and yaw, respectively (see also Section 4.1.3), ρ is the water density, and ω is the wave frequency (in rad/s). Also, WEC-Sim requires the hydrostatic stiffness matrix $C_{i,j}$ and coordinates of centre of buoyancy evaluated in the BEM solver based on the mean body wetted surface.

3.2 Hydrodynamics

Following the overview of the fundamental theory behind the BEM solvers (Section 3.1), the present subsection focuses on the application of this theory to WEC-Sim, describing the specific hydrodynamic calculations performed in the software.

Any physical body in the WEC system that contains a *Rigid Body* structural component (see also Section 3.3) may be assigned hydrodynamic properties, thereby allowing WEC-Sim to compute BEM-based, first-order hydrodynamic forces on the body. The force calculation is completed computing the excitation force (i.e. the force that would be experienced by the body if it were held stable in response to incoming waves, also referred to as diffraction force), the radiation force (i.e. the force reacting against the body as a result of its own motion in an otherwise undisturbed flow field), which in turn is related to the body dynamics, and the hydrostatic (buoyancy related) force. The fundamental hydrodynamic properties are computed by the flow solver (e.g. NEMOH) and, as a result, the WEC geometry itself is not an input to WEC-Sim in its linear equivalent. However, should weakly nonlinear hydrodynamic forces be considered, the full WEC geometry is required as an input (see Section 4.2.1).

WEC-Sim requires the non-dimensionalised hydrodynamic coefficients and scales the hydrodynamic coefficients according to the scaling method defined below, where g is modulus of the acceleration of gravity:

$$|F_{exc,i}(\omega)| = \frac{|F_{exc,i}(\omega)|}{\rho g} \quad (5)$$

$$\overline{A_{i,j}(\omega)} = \frac{A_{i,j}(\omega)}{\rho} \quad (6)$$

$$\overline{B_{i,j}(\omega)} = \frac{B_{i,j}(\omega)}{\rho\omega} \quad (7)$$

$$\overline{C_{i,j}} = \frac{C_{i,j}}{\rho g} \quad (8)$$

The non-dimensionalisation is performed as a pre-processing step in BEMIO, that formats the hydrodynamic data prior to running the WEC-Sim simulations (see also Section 4.2.4).

Using the hydrodynamic coefficients, the hydrodynamic forces are determined under the linear wave theory superposition assumption, which dictates that irregular waves can be obtained via the sum of incident, radiated, and diffracted wave components. The excitation force F_{exc} , radiation force F_{rad} , and buoyancy restoring force F_B of the equation of motion are calculated using the hydrodynamic coefficients provided by the frequency-domain BEM solver (see Section 3.1). In general, the buoyancy term F_B depends on the hydrostatic stiffness $C_{i,j}$ coefficients, as well as the body's displacement and mass.

3.2.1 Radiation force

Using the radiation damping coefficient, the radiation Impulse Response Function (IRF) K_r can be derived following:

$$K_{r_{i,j}}(t) = \frac{2g}{\pi} \int_0^\infty B_{i,j} \cdot \cos(\omega t) d\omega \quad (9)$$

Following the convolution integral formulation (see also Section 2.2), fluid memory effects acting on the system can be estimated based on the Cummins equation [Cummins, 1962]. The radiation term includes the added-mass matrix $A(\omega)$, and the radiation damping term, matrix $B(\omega)$, associated with the acceleration and velocity of the floating body, respectively. The radiation term can be calculated by:

$$F_{rad}(t) = -A_\infty \ddot{X} - \int_0^t K_r(t - \tau) \dot{X}(\tau) d\tau \quad (10)$$

where A_∞ is the added mass matrix at infinite frequency.

3.2.2 Wave Excitation Force and Weakly Nonlinear Approach

The wave excitation term $F_{exc}(\omega)$ includes a Froude-Krylov force component, generated by the undisturbed incident waves and therefore solely related to the incident fluid field, and a diffraction component, generated by the presence of the body when subject to incident waves.

When calculating the wave excitation force, a ramp function R_f is implemented to avoid strong transients at the initial instants of the simulation. The ramp function is given by:

$$R_f = \begin{cases} 1/2(1 + \cos(\pi + \frac{\pi t}{t_r})) & \frac{t}{t_r} < 1 \\ 1 & \frac{t}{t_r} \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where t is the simulation time and t_r is the ramp time.

The excitation force can then be calculated as the real part of an integral term across all wave frequencies, as follows:

$$F_{exc}(t) = \Re \left[R_f \int_0^{\infty} F_{exc}(\omega_r) e^{i(\omega_r t + \phi)} \sqrt{2S(\omega_r)} d\omega_r \right] \quad (12)$$

where ϕ is the phase angle and $S(\omega)$ is the wave spectrum describing the wave energy distribution over a range of wave frequencies (see also Section 4.1.4).

3.2.3 Nonlinear Effects

As mentioned in Section 2.3, large body motions, which may occur e.g. as a result of low PTO damping or the excitation of resonant modes, can lead to significant nonlinearities in the WEC response. In order to account for such effects, the MegaRoller WEC-Sim model will be able to consider a number of nonlinear forces, namely:

- Nonlinear Froude-Krylov hydrodynamics and hydrostatics (see Section 3.2.3.1).
- Additional added-mass and viscous damping forces (see Section 3.2.3.2).
- Slap and slam forces (see Section 3.2.3.3).

These nonlinear forces are further described in the subsection below.

3.2.3.1 Nonlinear Buoyancy and Froude-Krylov Components

A weakly nonlinear approach can be used to account for the nonlinear hydrodynamic forces induced by the instantaneous water surface elevation and body position. Using this formulation, the nonlinear buoyancy and the Froude-Krylov force components can be obtained by integrating the static and dynamic pressures over each panel along the wetted body surface at each time step.

The static and dynamic pressures are respectively given by:

$$p_{hs} = \rho g z \quad (13)$$

$$p_{hd} = \frac{1}{2} \rho g H \frac{\cosh(k(z+d))}{\cosh(kd)} \cos(\theta) \quad (14)$$

where ρ is the fluid density, g is the acceleration resulting from gravity, H is the wave height, k is the wave number, d is the mean water depth, z is the vertical coordinate, and θ is the wave phase angle.

Because linear wave theory is used to determine the flow velocity and pressure field, the values can become unrealistically large for wetted panels that are above the mean water level. To correct this, the Wheeler stretching method can be applied [Wheeler, 1969], correcting the instantaneous wave elevation that forces its height to equal to the water depth when calculating the flow velocity and pressure:

$$z^* = \frac{d(d+z)}{d+\eta} - d \quad (15)$$

where η is the z-value on the instantaneous water surface.

3.2.3.2 Drag Force

Because BEM codes are potential flow solvers and neglect the effects of viscosity, a drag force F_v generally must be included to accurately model device response (see Section 2.2). Essentially, the drag coefficients depend on the device geometry, scale and relative velocity between the body and the fluid around it. Empirical data on applicable drag coefficients can be found in various literature and standards for simple geometries (e.g. DNV-RP-H103), or can be derived from e.g. computational fluid dynamic simulations or experimental data. The drag force can then be estimated following:

$$F_v = -C_v|\dot{X}| - \frac{C_d\rho A_d}{2}\dot{X}|\dot{X}| \quad (16)$$

where C_v is the linear damping coefficient, C_d is the quadratic drag coefficient, ρ is the fluid density, A_d is the characteristic area for drag calculation and \dot{X} is the relative velocity between the body and the flow around it.

It is noted that the default implementation in WEC-Sim considers the absolute body velocity rather than the relative velocity between the body and the fluid around it. This default formulation was used as a first approximation in the initial simulations documented in Section 5. An updated formulation, which considers the relative velocity, was implemented by CA and is available for simulations using standard shaped waves (regular or standard shaped spectrum).

3.2.3.3 Slap and Slam Effects

Slap and slam are physical phenomena that may occur due to sudden retardation of a volume of fluid, being usually associated to events that involve sudden wave impacts on the surface of a body, or when a body suddenly enters the water at significant speed. In general, slam refers to events when the body hits the free-surface on a plane parallel to the mean free-surface (e.g. body falling into undisturbed water), while slap refers to events when the water hits the body on a plane approximately perpendicular to the wave propagation direction – see e.g. Figure 3.1. The consideration of slap and slam forces may be relevant when attempting to improve the fidelity of load estimates on floating bodies in aggressive environmental conditions (see also Section 2.3).

Figure 3.1 Slam (left) and slap (right) events – illustrative cases for a pitching flap

CA have incorporated an empirical correction to implement the effect of slam and slap forces in WEC-Sim. The implementation allows estimates of the pressure distribution over the body during slam and slap events to be obtained, as described in this subsection.

Slam Forces

The formulation implemented by CA addresses the local slam force applicable to a body panel at the instant of the impact, i.e. when the centroid of the panel enters the water. As an initial assumption, the slam forces in such events are taken as proportional to the square of the relative velocity between the body and the fluid. Consequently, the local slam forces at the body panels can be estimated by:

$$\overrightarrow{F_{slam}}(t = t_{impact}) = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_{pa} A_n v_n^2 \vec{n} \quad (17)$$

where ρ is the fluid density, C_{pa} is the non-dimensional space averaged pressure coefficient, A_n is the dot product between the panel area vector and \vec{n} , v_n is the projection of the relative velocity between the body and the fluid at the centroid of the panel in the direction of \vec{n} , and \vec{n} is the unit vector in the outward normal direction of the free-surface at the body panel centroid.

Slap Forces

In a similar way to the slam force formulation described above, the slap force can be estimated via:

$$\overrightarrow{F_{slap}}(t = t_{impact}) = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_{pa} A_t v_t^2 \vec{t} \quad (18)$$

where A_t is the dot product between the panel area vector and \vec{t} , v_t is the projection of the relative velocity between the body and the fluid at the centroid of the panel in the direction of \vec{t} , and \vec{t} is the unit vector in the tangent direction to the free-surface at the body panel centroid (following the wave propagation direction).

3.3 Structural Dynamics

3.3.1 A Multi-Body Structural Analysis Approach

WEC-Sim uses a multi-body structural analysis approach, where the system is defined in terms of a number of constituent components (or '*bodies*'), each of which is a mathematical model containing information about the body's own physical structure, expressed as a set of component differential equations. The use of a multi-body structural engine means that users are able to build a structural model of a WEC as a collection of interconnected components, which can rotate or translate relative to one another. This approach allows the baseline tool to support a wide range of WEC concepts, reflecting the range of designs being developed throughout the industry and benefiting from a wider range of validation data sources.

In its current formulation, the WEC structural properties are represented in WEC-Sim as rigid bodies with mass, inertia, PTO and hydrodynamic properties. The components of a time-domain multi-body dynamics model of a WEC are taken from a pre-built WEC library containing time-domain modules that represent the relevant physics for that component. The WEC-Sim library is divided into five different types of library blocks, briefly described below:

- The Body Elements library contains the Rigid Body block used to simulate the different bodies. In particular, the body block representing the WEC rigid body contains the HydroForce module components that model hydrodynamic forces on the body.

- The Frames library contains the Global Reference Frame block necessary for every simulation, and defines the global coordinates, solver configuration, seabed and free-surface description, simulation time, and other global settings.
- The Constraints library contains blocks that are used to constrain the DOF of the bodies without including any additional forcing or resistance.
- The PTOs library contains blocks used to both simulate a PTO system and restrict the body motion.

The relative position of each body is defined by the location of their centre of gravity in the global reference frame. The component connectivity is defined in the constraint and PTO classes that connect the bodies to the global reference frame. For constraints and PTOs, the user also needs to specify their location with respect to the global reference frame (see also Section 4).

At the structural definition level, the WEC interconnected components are combined into a set of complete system differential equations in terms of their generalised freedom(s). These equations are then solved by the numerical integrator during the simulation, which iteratively solves the equations at each timestep. At the beginning of a time step, the solutions are passed from the integrator to the structural module so that a complete new set of constraint reaction forces may be calculated.

3.3.2 Flexible Structures

As described in Section 3.3.1, WEC-Sim currently implements a rigid body dynamics approach where each hydrodynamic body is treated as a point with mass and inertia. However, to assess the influence of the hydrodynamic loads on the WEC structure in terms of deformation of its external surfaces, both the structural and hydrodynamic responses must be solved simultaneously. Hydrodynamic loads could also excite fundamental frequencies of the structure, leading to resonance and potentially the destruction of the device.

In order to assess the effects of the distributed loading contributions over the flap on the PTO system, it is envisaged that an advanced structural dynamics module is implemented in WEC-Sim. This section presents a summary of the research and work to date, outlining options for investigation as the MegaRoller project progresses.

3.3.2.1 Current State of the Art

Several software packages are currently used in the offshore industry to implement fluid-structure methods capable of accounting for flexible structures at different levels of fidelity. For example:

- Sesam / Bladed: Sesam can be configured to perform various functions [DNV GL, 2018], ranging from fully-coupled aero-hydro-servo-elastic analysis to a sequential approach where loads are calculated separately, where no hydro-elastic coupling is accounted for.
- HydroDyn / SubDyn: A structural add-on to the FAST suite of software for time-domain analysis of offshore wind turbines [Jonkman, 2014]. Strip theory is used to calculate hydrodynamic loads on the jacket (HydroDyn) which is then coupled to a dynamic structural solver (SubDyn).

Both of the above methods mostly rely on the Morrison equations to predict hydrodynamic loads. Although the Morrison coefficients can be calibrated using test data or higher-fidelity simulations, this may not be applicable for larger diffracting bodies. The codes mentioned above also have the ability to

implement a hybrid approach, where a combination of Morrison elements and potential-flow calculations are used. In such case, only the Morrison terms would be coupled to the structural deformation.

Previous work by Yi Guo et al. [Guo, 2017] has introduced a form of structural dynamics to WEC-Sim. A generalised body modes approach was taken, where the DOFs of the system were reduced based on the structure's modal response. Mode shapes were added as extra DOFs in WAMIT. They were also implemented within WEC-Sim, creating a flexible multi-body model. Results from two simple test cases are shown to match closely with higher fidelity models. However, the work relies on assumed deflected shapes. This is potentially difficult to generalise and / or to implement for more complex geometries.

3.3.2.2 WEC-Sim Implementation

In the context of the MegaRoller project, it is envisaged that the Finite-Element (FE) method is used to predict structural deformation. A simplified, low-fidelity FE model with few elements and only an outline representation of the structure is therefore acceptable without reducing overall model accuracy.

When considering the structural dynamic response of a structure, and if the natural frequencies of the structure are larger than the loading frequency (ratio above three used in the FEA best practice document from ANSYS⁵), inertial and damping effects can generally be neglected to reduce computational effort, leading to a static solution. For a linear static analysis, the solution at each time step is independent of the previous timestep, depending only on the stiffness and applied load. It is envisaged that both static and dynamic solvers will be investigated further as the project progresses.

In a first stage, the structural analysis can be run as a standalone post-processing step using the pressure and force time-series output by WEC-Sim (see Figure 3.2). This can be accomplished using most FEA packages with little modification, however such approach does not include any coupled fluid-structure interaction effects.

Figure 3.2 Standalone post-processing step – uncoupled approach

In a second stage, a coupled approach can be considered. In [Ahamed, 2017], one-way (loosely coupled) and two-way (strongly coupled) implementations are considered:

- In the loosely coupled approach, the loads and deformation are only calculated once at each time step.
- In the strongly coupled approach, the analysis iterates at each time step until forces converge.

As a first approximation, it is proposed to use a loosely coupled approach to match the approach followed by WEC-Sim when interfacing with MoorDyn (see Figure 3.3). Such approach requires relatively small

⁵ ANSYS FEA Best practices http://innomet.ttu.ee/martin/MER0070/Loengud/FEA_Best_Practices.pdf

time-steps to ensure the change in force and deformation at each step is small. Furthermore, it is envisaged that only a subset of the hydrodynamic force components is updated. In particular, the nonlinear hydrostatic and Froude-Krylov forces are immediately coupled by providing displacement estimates back to WEC-Sim at each time step (see the ‘*Subset option*’ branch in Figure 3.3). Updating the radiation and added-mass forces would be more difficult and computationally expensive, as the hydrodynamic coefficients would require updating at each time step (see the ‘*All hydrodynamics option*’ branch in Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3 Loosely coupled approach

It is envisaged that the flexible structure feature will be added to the MegaRoller WEC model and tested as the project progresses. The different approaches outlined above will be trialled to assess the sensitivity of MegaRoller to the model fidelity and determine the optimal balance between accuracy and computational effort.

3.4 Power-Take-Off (PTO) and Control

The PTO forms part of a WEC’s power conversion chain (PCC), usually being a primary system that converts the mechanical motion of the WEC into electrical power. The majority of WECs convert the energy from the wave into either relative linear motion, relative rotary motion, or fluid capture. This mechanical power is then converted into electrical power through the PTO.

As a default, the WEC-Sim code enables the modelling of PTOs as a simple linear spring-damper, where the reaction force is given by:

$$F_{PTO} = -K_{PTO}X_{rel} - C_{PTO}\dot{X}_{rel} \quad (19)$$

where K_{PTO} and C_{PTO} are the stiffness and damping coefficients of the PTO, respectively, and X_{rel} and \dot{X}_{rel} are the relative motion and velocity, respectively.

In these approximations, the instantaneous power absorbed by the PTO is then given by:

$$P_{PTO} = C_{PTO}\dot{X}_{rel}^2 \quad (20)$$

Alternatively, WEC-Sim also enables the modelling of other PCCs such as mechanical and / or hydraulic drivetrains, through the use of native Simulink blocks coupled with WEC-Sim’s user-defined PTO blocks. The WEC-Sim response (relative displacement and velocity for linear motion and angular position and velocity for rotary motion) is the input to the PCC, whilst the PTO force or torque is in return the WEC-Sim

input. In particular, PTO-Sim is the WEC-Sim module responsible for accurately modelling a WEC's conversion of mechanical power to electrical power through its PTO system [So, 2015]. It consists of a library of PTO component blocks that can be linked together to model different PTO systems. Each of these PTO library blocks is a model of common PTO components, such as electric generators, pistons, and accumulators.

For oscillating wave surge converters (OWSC) such as the MegaRoller WEC, the electricity is converted from the back-and-forth movement of the bottom-mounted flap. The design of the MegaRoller PTO (hydraulic components, e.g. cylinders, manifolds, accumulators, and electrical aspects including the innovative twin drive-train) will be the focus of WP2. It is anticipated that the PTO design effort conducted in WP2 will continually inform the PTO block in the MegaRoller WEC-Sim model.

In the preliminary simulations documented in this report, and following the tank experiments at Queen's University of Belfast (see Section 5), the target PTO profile was defined as a Coulomb damping force acting in opposite direction of the angular velocity of the flap in pitch. However, the experimental measurements evidenced significant variations in PTO torque with the absolute angular velocity, in particular in large waves (see for example Figure 3.4). Therefore, the PTO model considered in the pre-validation case study of the WaveRoller WEC documented in this report considered a look-up table summarising the PTO torque with the angular velocity of the flap in pitch (see also Section 4.4).

Figure 3.4 Example of measured PTO torque time-series (left) and profile vs. angular pitch velocity (right) – Test ID 049A (target saturation threshold of PTO torque in red)

4 BUILDING A WEC-SIM MODEL

Practical background information on the WEC-Sim code is provided in Section 4.1, including details of the key steps required to install WEC-Sim, followed by an introduction on the code structure and conventions.

Aspects associated with the input structure of the WEC-Sim model are then provided, including:

- The preparation of the model geometry and hydrodynamic properties (Section 4.2).
- The construction of the multi-body dynamics model of the WEC (Section 4.3).
- Items specifically related to the PTO and control models (Section 4.4).
- The preparation of the WEC-Sim input file (Section 4.5).

Finally, the simulation outputs are briefly overviewed in Section 4.6

Although this section exemplifies the functionalities and steps required to setup a model that replicates the WaveRoller WEC design tested in the Queen’s University of Belfast, it should be noted that the essential steps described in this section are applicable when considering version of MegaRoller WEC-Sim model.

4.1 Background: Handling WEC-Sim

4.1.1 Software Installation

WEC-Sim is developed in MATLAB/Simulink, and requires the toolboxes listed below. WEC-Sim’s Simulink Library was saved in MATLAB version R2015b, thus this is the oldest MATLAB release compatible with WEC-Sim. It is recommend running WEC-Sim in MATLAB 2016b or newer.

Table 4.1 Required toolbox and versions compatible with WEC-Sim

Required Toolbox	Oldest Compatible Version
MATLAB	Version 8.6 (R2015b)
Simulink	Version 8.6 (R2015b)
Simscape	Version 3.14 (R2015b)
Simscape Multibody	Version 4.7 (R2015b)

The user can confirm that the correct version of MATLAB and the required toolboxes are installed by typing `ver` in the MATLAB Command Window.

4.1.2 WEC-Sim Code Structure

The numerical model is implemented using the modular structure shown in Figure 4.1. Following the key user inputs in terms of device and simulation specifications, WEC-Sim modules are divided into three types:

1. Pre-processing modules are executed once at the beginning of a simulation to prepare user input data, and perform calculations that are not time-dependent.

2. Time-domain modules simulate specific device components and solve the equation of motion to model the WEC system (see Section 3.1).
3. Post-processing modules are responsible for visualisation and simulation data analysis.

Figure 4.1 The WEC-Sim code structure: User inputs (dark blue), Pre-processing modules (light blue), Time-domain modules (green) and Post-processing modules (red) [Yu, 2014]

Figure 4.2 illustrates the steps in creating a WEC-Sim simulation. Sections 4.2 to 4.6 provide further details regarding these basic steps, describing how the WEC-Sim model is built in the MATLAB framework.

Figure 4.2 The key steps to build and run a WEC-Sim model

The remainder of this subsection (Sections 4.1.3 and 4.1.4) details the coordinate system, conventions used and the definition of the wave environment in WEC-Sim.

4.1.3 Conventions in WEC-Sim

The coordinate system used in WEC-Sim is defined in Figure 4.3 for a generic floating body subject to incoming waves. The WEC-Sim coordinate system assumes that the positive x -axis defines a wave angle heading of zero (e.g. a wave propagating with along a zero-degree heading is moving in the positive x direction). The z -axis is in the vertical upwards direction, and the y -axis direction is defined by the right-hand rule.

Figure 4.3 WEC-Sim coordinate system

In the vectors and matrices used in WEC-Sim, surge (x), sway (y), and heave (z) correspond to the first, second and third position, respectively. Roll (R_x), pitch (R_y), and yaw (R_z) correspond to the fourth, fifth and sixth position, respectively.

All units within WEC-Sim are in the MKS (meters-kilograms-seconds) system and angular measurements are specified in radians, except for wave directionality which is defined in degrees.

4.1.4 Wave Environment Definition

In WEC-Sim, both regular and irregular unidirectional waves can be defined as incident wave conditions for the time-domain simulations.

For regular waves, the incident wave is defined as:

$$\eta(x, t) = \frac{H}{2} \cos(\omega t - kx + \phi) \quad (21)$$

where H is the wave height, ω is the wave frequency, k is the wave number, and ϕ is the wave phase.

For irregular waves, the incident wave is typically defined by a wave spectrum, where individual sinusoidal waves of different amplitudes and periods are superimposed. Three common types of spectra are readily available in WEC-Sim, namely the Pierson-Moskowitz spectrum, the two-parameter Bretschneider spectrum and the JONSWAP spectrum. All are defined in WEC-Sim by their peak period and significant wave height. Optionally, the user may also input the incident spectrum or incident time series of wave elevation (see also Section 4.5.2).

4.2 Hydrodynamic Model

The bodies in a WEC-Sim model affected by wave loading may be assigned hydrodynamic and hydrostatic properties. The hydrodynamic loading is obtained using a BEM solver that is able to calculate the first-order hydrodynamic body properties, including diffraction and radiation effects, of a large range of arbitrary geometries, enabling also the consideration of multiple bodies and of their interactions (see Section 3.2).

This section describes the application of the NEMOH code and the WEC-Sim pre-processing steps to obtain the hydrodynamic coefficients and generate the data structure compatible with the WEC-Sim input requirements. The subsequent subsections adhere to the process schematised in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4 WEC-Sim pre-processing steps to generate frequency-domain hydrodynamic coefficients

4.2.1 Mesh Generation

To generate hydrodynamic coefficients, a BEM solver requires the wetted profile of the bodies and their position in the global coordinate system as input. Typically, the geometry is provided in a geometric data file format (*.gdf), which can be exported from commercial CAD application software. For NEMOH, the mesh is generated using low-order (flat) panels. It should be noted that NEMOH can handle a maximum of 3,000 panels per body. For convenience, in the example provided in this section the mesh has its origin at the free-surface. The coordinates of the centres of mass of each body are provided in the NEMOH input file (see Section 4.2.2).

STL-files (*.stl) of each body, required for the WEC-Sim simulation (see also Section 4.5.3), are also generated in CAD software. WEC-Sim imposes that the origin of each STL-file sits at the centre of mass of the body, with the axes aligned with the WEC-Sim convention (see Section 4.1.3) The . STL files should be saved using ASCII format. Figure 4.5 illustrates the geometry and full-scale equivalent dimensions of the model tested in the tank in Belfast, used in the case study presented in Section 5.

Figure 4.5 WEC geometry (front and right views) and full-scale equivalent dimensions

4.2.2 BEM Solver Setup

In the current release of WEC-Sim, hydrodynamic coefficients obtained from the BEM solvers WAMIT, AQWA and NEMOH can be imported. This section describes the steps required to setup a NEMOH simulation to generate the hydrodynamic coefficients for the WaveRoller WEC.

A NEMOH simulation folder must be created, including the inputs to be read by NEMOH and a destination for the outputs that will be generated. Such folder must contain the following:

- A **Meshfile** folder, containing the *mesh.exe* NEMOH routine.
- A **NEMOH** folder, containing the pre-processing, solver and post-processing NEMOH executable files.
- A **NEMOHcase** folder (name at user's discretion), that will include the NEMOH input and output files.
 - The folder must be prepared with (empty) **mesh** and **results** folders.
- The geometry data file *.gdf for each body.
- *run_gdf.py*, a Python script that converts the geometric data file to a NEMOH-compatible mesh.
- *mesh_view.m*, a MATLAB script that enables the visualisation of the NEMOH-compatible mesh.
- *run_mesh.m*, a MATLAB script that sets-up the frequencies, directions and water depth inputs for running NEMOH (see Section 4.2.3).
 - The function calls the *NEMOH1.m* MATLAB script that runs NEMOH.
- *run_wecsim_bemio.m*, a MATLAB script that generates a data structure compatible with WEC-Sim (see Section 4.2.4).
 - The function calls the *read_NEMOH.m* MATLAB script that reads the NEMOH outputs.

The *run_gdf.py* Python script prepares the inputs files for NEMOH. The function requires the path and names of the NEMOH case folder, the names of the geometry data files, the coordinates of the centre of mass for each body in the *.gdf coordinate system, along with other inputs such as the target number of panels for the mesh. The key required inputs are detailed in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2 Inputs required for the run_gdf.py script

<code>path11 = 'E:\\NEMOHtuto\\NEMOHfiles\\'</code>	<i>Path to the NEMOH runs folder</i>
<code>foldername11 = 'NEMOHcase'</code>	<i>Name of the NEMOHcase folder</i>
<code>ifile1 = open(path11+'Panel_depth14.5m.gdf','r')</code>	<i>Opens the first geometry data file</i>
<code>ifile2 = open(path11+'Base_depth14.5m.gdf','r')</code>	<i>Opens the second geometry data file</i>
<code>nbodies = 2</code>	<i>Number of bodies</i>
<code>cg_input = np.array([[0,-1.729,-6.216],[5,0,-12.5]])</code>	<i>Coordinates of the centres of mass</i>
<code>rho_water = 1025</code>	<i>Water density</i>
<code>g = 9.81</code>	<i>Gravity acceleration</i>
<code>body_sym = [0,0]</code>	<i>Mesh x-axis symmetries (for each body)</i>
<code>tx = [0,0]</code>	<i>Translation in x-axis from origin (for each body)</i>
<code>ty = [0,0]</code>	<i>Translation in y-axis from origin (for each body)</i>
<code>np_target = [2510,1184]</code>	<i>Target number of panels (for each body)</i>

The function first creates a text file *ID.dat* that contains the name of the NEMOH case folder. Then, the function creates, in a loop for each hydrodynamic body, a *mesh.cal* file describing the mesh input parameters, as described in Table 4.3, and runs the NEMOH mesh routine *mesh.exe*.

Table 4.3 Details of the mesh.cal file

mesh2	<i>Mesh file name</i>
1	<i>Mesh x-axis symmetric (=1 yes, =0 no)</i>
0.0 0.0	<i>(x, y) mesh translation from origin</i>
0.0 0.0 -12.5	<i>CoG coordinates (x, y, z)</i>
1184	<i>Mesh target number of panels</i>
2	<i>Unused line</i>
0.	<i>Mesh z-axis translation from origin</i>
1.	<i>Mesh scale factor</i>
1025.0	<i>Water density</i>
9.81	<i>Gravity acceleration</i>

The mesh output files, saved in the **mesh** folder of the NEMOH case folder, include the following files, with 'xx' corresponding to the body number (in Python numbering, i.e. from 0 to nbodies-1):

- *Hydrostatics_xx.dat* – buoyancy centre, displaced volume and waterplane area.
- *Description_Full_xx.tec* and *Description_Wetted_xx.tec* – body input description.
- *GC_hull_xx.dat* and *Inertia_hull_xx.dat* – centre of gravity and inertia matrix. The solver assumes that the mass is equal to the displacement and that the mass is distributed at the body surface.
- *KH_xx.dat* – hydrostatic stiffness matrix.
- *meshxx*, *meshxx.dat* and *meshxx.tec* – NEMOH input mesh file and Tecplot mesh format.
- *meshxx_info.dat* – mesh number of points and panels.

The resulting mesh used in the pre-validation case study documented in this report is shown in Figure 4.6 (see also Section 4.5).

Figure 4.6 Example of the NEMOH mesh defined for the WaveRoller WEC used in the pre-validation exercise

Finally, the function prepares the *Nemoh.cal* file, saved in the NEMOH case folder, that includes the inputs for NEMOH (except the frequencies, directions and water depth inputs).

4.2.3 Running the BEM Solver

As mentioned in the previous section, the case study presented in this report generated the hydrodynamic coefficients (added mass, radiation damping, and wave excitation) using the BEM solver NEMOH.

The NEMOH solver is executed by running the MATLAB script *NEMOH.m*, providing it with the water depth, wave frequencies and wave directions inputs. The script then executes the NEMOH program, in the three following steps:

- Pre-processing: execute *preProcessor.exe* that setups the calculation cases.
- Solving: execute *Solver.exe* that solves the linear Laplace's equation for the potential and calculates the pressure field, the hydrodynamic coefficients, far field coefficients and wave elevation.
- Post-processing (optional): executes *postprocessor.exe* that derives relevant outputs, e.g. Response Amplitude Operators (RAOs).

The solver outputs a number of files, saved in the **results** folder of the NEMOH case folder, that are then post-processed by BEMIO to generate a data structure compatible with WEC-Sim, as described in the following subsection.

4.2.4 Preparing the Hydrodynamic Coefficients for WEC-Sim

The hydrodynamic data for each body must be parsed into a HDF5 file using the BEMIO hydrodynamic data format. The HDF5 file (*.h5) is created based on the BEM solutions (from NEMOH, WAMIT or AQWA) of the WEC geometry, using the *run_wecsim_bemio.m* MATLAB routine.

The *run_wecsim_bemio.m* MATLAB routine reads the NEMOH output located in the folder targeted in the script using the function:

```
hydro = Read_NEMOH(hydro, '\NEMOHcase\')
```

The routine then calculates the radiation and excitation IRFs:

```
hydro = Radiation_IRF(hydro, tend, nt, nw, wmin, wmax)  
hydro = Excitation_IRF(hydro, tend, nt, nw, wmin, wmax)
```

where *hydro* is the hydrodynamic data structure, *tend* is the IRF length, *nt* and *nw* are the number of time-steps and frequencies (default is 1001), *wmin* and *wmax* are the minimum and maximum frequencies to be used in the IRF calculation (default is BEM frequency range).

Finally, the HDF5 file is saved in the **hydroData** directory:

```
Write_H5(hydro)
```

Optionally, the user can plot the hydrodynamic data (i.e. added-mass, radiation damping, radiation IRF, excitation force magnitude and phase and excitation IRF) using the following function:

```
Plot_BEMIO(hydro)
```


Figure 4.7 to Figure 4.10 illustrate the resulting plots for the pre-validation case study documented in this report (see Section 5).

Figure 4.7 Normalised added mass in surge (left), heave (middle) and pitch (right) for the flap (blue) and foundation (red) bodies

Figure 4.8 Normalised excitation IRF in surge (left), heave (middle) and pitch (right) for the flap (blue) and foundation (red) bodies

Figure 4.9 Normalised radiation damping in surge (left), heave (middle) and pitch (right) for the flap (blue) and foundation (red) bodies

Figure 4.10 Normalised radiation IRF in surge (left), heave (middle) and pitch (right) for the flap (blue) and foundation (red) bodies

4.3 Structural Model

The WEC-Sim Simulink model is based on MATLAB Simscape Multibody (formerly SimMechanics) that represents multibody systems using blocks representing rigid bodies, constraints, force elements and sensors.

The WEC-Sim toolbox contains the following block types:

- Custom body blocks capable of applying hydrodynamic loads. Where required, body blocks can also be configured as non-hydrodynamic bodies.
- Constraint blocks that provide the DoF required in the WEC operation e.g. 6DoF floating.
- PTO blocks for translational and rotational operations, with the option of using external actuation force or prescribed motion.

Each body, constraint and PTO block generate output timeseries with block kinematics and loads after simulation. It is noted that WEC-Sim body blocks generate outputs based on the global reference frame. Constraint and PTO blocks generate outputs using the local reference frame

To create the time-domain multi-body dynamics model of the device, the user must drag the appropriate number of bodies, joints and connections from a library of pre-built WEC components into the WEC-Sim Simulink model (*.slx file), and connect these according to their physical layout. In the pre-validation case study documented in this report (see Section 5), the WEC is initially modelled as a rigid body block that simulates the flap connected via a single rotational pitching PCC block to a rigid body, the foundation, connected to the seabed. Figure 4.11 illustrates the corresponding Simulink model.

Figure 4.11 Schematic of the WEC-Sim model

To create the Simulink model, the user must open a new Simulink file and follow the steps listed below:

1. Open the WEC-Sim library browser by clicking . The window illustrated in Figure 4.12 opens:

Figure 4.12 Simulink library browser

2. Place two Rigid Body blocks from the *Body Elements* of the WEC-Sim Library in the Simulink model file.
Double click on each Rigid Body block in the Simulink model file and rename the corresponding instance of the body. "*body(1)*" must correspond to the first body in the BEM simulation (in this case, the flap) , whilst the second body (in this case, the foundation) should be called "*body(2)*".

3. Place the Global Reference Frame from the *Frames* of the WEC-Sim Library in the Simulink model file. The global reference frame acts as the seabed.
4. Place the Fixed block from the *Constraints* of the WEC-Sim Library in the Simulink model file. Connect the forward node (F) of the block to the foundation block and the back node (B) to the seabed.
5. Place a Rotational PTO Actuation Torque block from the *PTOs* of the WEC-Sim Library in the Simulink model file. Connect the forward node (F) to the flap block to the flap block and the back node (B) to the foundation block. The PTO block is further described in Section 4.4.

4.4 Power-Take-Off (PTO) and Control Model

The functionality of the PTO block is two-fold: first, to constrain the flap motion to pitch only; second, to extract power from relative body motion with respect to the reference frame.

In the tank experiments at Queen’s University of Belfast, the target PTO profile was defined as a Coulomb damping force acting in direction opposing the flap pitch angular velocity signal. A PTO torque look-up-table function was defined as input to the pre-validation model of the WaveRoller WEC documented in this report (see Section 5), using a smoothed signal of the measured PTO torque vs. flap pitch angular velocity profile.

The Simulink model of the PTO is provided in Figure 4.13. The model uses a bus and selector block that selects the velocity in pitch, and a look-up-table block feeding back to the torque input. The look-up-table block reads a MATLAB structure *PTOexp_lookuptable* with two fields: the smoothed signal of the measured torque *PTOtorque*, and the corresponding pitch velocity *vel*. The look-up-table block then applies an interpolated torque signal. Sign conventions are such that a positive PTO force value opposes a negative velocity, and vice-versa.

Figure 4.13 Schematic of the WEC-Sim PTO model

To create the PTO model, the user must follow the steps listed below:

1. In the existing Simulink model, open the WEC-Sim library browser by clicking .
2. Place a *Bus Selector* from the *Signal Routing* of the Simulink Library. Connect its input to the *Response* output of the Rotational PTO Actuation Torque block.
3. Double click on the *Bus Selector* block and select the velocity as the signal in the bus. Apply and close the Block parameters window.
4. Place a *Selector* from the *Signal Routing* of the Simulink Library. Connect its input to the *Bus Selector* output.
5. Double click on the *Selector* block and type *1* for the “*number of input dimension*”, select “*one-based*” for the index mode, and type *5* in the index to indicate the selection of the fifth component of the velocity signal (velocity in pitch).
6. Place a *1D Lookup Table* from the *Lookup Tables* of the Simulink Library. Connect its input to the *Selector* output.
7. Double click on the *1D Lookup Table* block and type the name of the MATLAB variable containing the PTO torque values in the *Table data* field, and the name of the MATLAB file variable containing the corresponding velocities of the flap in pitch in the *Breakpoint 1* field.
8. Connect the *1D Lookup Table* block to the torque input of the Rotational PTO Actuation Torque block.

4.5 Simulation Setup

The WEC-Sim source code consists of a series of MATLAB objects (defined in WEC-Sim as Classes) and Simulink library blocks which are executed by the *wecSim.m* script. Executing *wecSim.m* parses the user input data, performs pre-processing calculations in each of the classes, selects and initialises variant subsystems in the Simulink model, and runs the time-domain simulations in WEC-Sim.

All information required to run the WEC-Sim simulations is contained within the *simu*, *waves*, *body(i)*, *pto(i)* and *constraint(i)* objects (instances of the *simulationClass*, *waveClass*, *bodyClass*, *ptoClass* and *constraintClass*, *ptoClass*). The user can interact with these classes within the WEC-Sim input file *wecSimInputFile.m*. This section aims to describe the role of the WEC-Sim objects, and how to interact with the WEC-Sim objects to define input properties.

There are two ways to check the available properties and methods within a class. The first is to type *doc <className>* in MATLAB Command Window, and the second is to open the class definitions located in the *//WEC-Sim/source/objects* directory by typing *open <className>* in MATLAB Command Window. The latter provides more information, as it also defines the different fields in a structure.

4.5.1 Simulation Control Parameters: Simulation Class

The simulation class contains the key simulation parameters and solver settings necessary to execute the WEC-Sim code such as the Simulink model filename or the simulation time-step and duration. Within the *wecSimInputFile.m*, users must initialise the simulation class and specify the name of the Simulink WEC-Sim model file by including the following lines:

```
simu = simulationClass();
simu.simMechanicsFile = '{WEC Model Name}.slx'
```


Users may specify other simulation class properties using the `simu` object in the `wecSimInputFile.m`, such as: simulation start time (`simu.startTime`), end time (`simu.endTime`), ramp time (`simu.rampTime`) and time step (`simu.dt`).

The values used for the key simulation properties are described in Table 4.4. Other simulation properties used the WEC-Sim default values where required, that can be found by typing `doc simulationClass` in the MATLAB command window.

Table 4.4 Simulation properties defined in the Simulation Class

Simulation property	Command and Value
Specify Simulink Model File	<code>simu.simMechanicsFile = 'MEG1_v3_PTOMEASURED.slx';</code>
Simulation Start Time [s]	<code>simu.startTime = 0;</code>
Wave Ramp Time [s]	<code>simu.rampTime = 384;</code>
Simulation End Time [s]	<code>simu.endTime = test_duration;</code>
Simulation Time-Step [s]	<code>simu.dt = 0.01;</code>
Specify CI Time [s]	<code>simu.CITime = 100;</code>
Nonlinear FK force*	<code>simu.nlHydro = 0;</code>
Option for body to body interactions	<code>simu.b2b = 1;</code>

* Note that for the nonlinear case (see Section 5.4), `simu.nlHydro = 1`

In the preliminary results presented in this section, the simulation end time (including the ramp time) was set as the record length in the tank experiments, defined relative to the type of environmental conditions considered (in equivalent full-scale dimensions): for regular waves, the duration of simulation in the tank was 1,152s; for irregular waves 1,920s; for extreme waves, 13,056s.

4.5.2 Generating Environmental Conditions: Wave Class

WEC-Sim can be used to run simulation in unidirectional regular waves, irregular sea-states and user defined time series. The wave class contains all wave information necessary to define the incident wave condition for the WEC-Sim time-domain simulation. Within the `wecSimInputFile.m`, users must initialise the wave class and specify the wave type by including the following lines:

```
waves = waveClass('type');
```

Users must specify additional wave class properties using the `waves` object depending on which wave type is selected, as shown in Table 4.5 below. A more detailed description of the wave types used in the present study is given in the following sections.

Table 4.5 Wave properties required in the Wave Class by wave type

Wave Type	Required Properties
noWave	waves.T
noWaveCIC	N/A
regular	waves.H, waves.T
regularCIC	waves.H, waves.T
irregular	waves.H, waves.T, waves.spectrumType
spectrumImport	waves.spectrumDataFile
etaImport	waves.etaDataFile

Other wave class properties, default values, and functions can be found by typing `doc waveClass` in the MATLAB command window.

The wave type and associated period and height properties considered are specified along with each result presented in Section 5.

4.5.2.1 Regular Waves

The regular wave case is for running simulations with regular waves and constant added mass and radiation damping coefficients. Using this option, WEC-Sim assumes that the system dynamic response is in sinusoidal steady-state form, where constant added mass and damping coefficients are used (instead of the convolution integral) to calculate wave radiation forces. Wave period (`wave.T`) and wave height (`wave.H`) must be specified in the input file.

The regular case is defined by including the following in the input file:

```
waves = waveClass('regular');
waves.T = <user specified wave period>;
waves.H = <user specified wave height>;
```

4.5.2.2 Irregular Spectrum

The irregular wave case is the wave type for irregular wave simulations using a Pierson Moskowitz (PM), Bretschneider (BS), or JONSWAP (JS) wave spectrum. Significant wave height (`wave.H`), peak period (`wave.T`), and wave spectrum type (`waves.spectrumType`) must be specified in the input file. The available wave spectra and their corresponding `waves.spectrumType` are listed in Table 4.6 below:

Table 4.6 Available spectrum types and abbreviation required in the `waves.spectrumType` variable

Wave Spectrum	spectrumType
Pierson Moskowitz	PM
Bretschneider	BS
JONSWAP	JS

The irregular case is defined by including the following in the input file:

```
waves = waveClass('irregular');
waves.T = <user specified wave period>;
waves.H = <user specified wave height>;
waves.spectrumType = '<user specified spectrum>';
waves.gamma = <user specified gamma>
```

4.5.2.3 User Defined Time Series of Sea Surface Elevation

The `etaImport` case is the wave type for wave simulations using user-defined time-series (ex: from experiments). The user-defined wave surface elevation must be defined with the time (s) in the first column, and the wave surface elevation (m) in the second column. The `etaImport` case is defined by including the following in the input file:

```
waves = waveClass('etaImport');
waves.etaDataFile = '<eta file>.mat';
```


4.5.3 WEC Properties Setup: Body, Constraint and PTO Classes

4.5.3.1 Body Class

The body class contains the mass and hydrodynamic properties of each body that comprises the WEC being simulated. Within the *wecSimInputFile.m*, users must initialise each iteration of the body class (*bodyClass*), and specify the location of the hydrodynamic data file (*.h5) and geometry file (*.stl) for each body. Note that the geometry file is mandatory only for nonlinear simulations. The body class is defined by including the following lines in the WEC-Sim input file, where # is the body number (*bem_data*) is the name of the h5 file containing the BEM results:

```
body((#)) = bodyClass('bem_data.h5')
body((#)).geometryFile = 'geom.stl';
```

Users may specify other body class properties using the body object for each body in the *wecSimInputFile.m*. WEC-Sim assumes that every WEC is composed of rigid bodies exposed to wave forcing. Body class properties include mass (*body((#)).mass*) and moment of inertia (*body((#)).momOfInertia*). For example, viscous drag can be specified by entering the viscous drag coefficient and the characteristic area in vector format the WEC-Sim input file as follows:

```
body((#)).viscDrag.cd = [cd1 cd2 cd3 cd4 cd5 cd6]
body((#)).viscDrag.characteristicArea = [a1 a2 a3 a4 a5 a6]
```

The values used for the key body properties are described in Table 4.7. Note that the values used were provided by AWE⁶ in full-scale equivalent (see also Section 5.1). Other body properties, default values, and functions can be found by typing *doc bodyClass* in the MATLAB command window.

Table 4.7 Body properties defined in the Body Class

Body property	Command and Value
Initialize bodyClass for Flap	<i>body(1) = bodyClass(h5_file);</i>
Geometry File	<i>body(1).geometryFile = 'geometry/cal_model - Panel2 - 1_0cdg.stl';</i>
User-Defined mass [kg]	<i>body(1).mass = 145540;</i>
Moment of Inertia [kg-m ²]	<i>body(1).momOfInertia = [9.945533e6 2.249467e6 9.948750e6];</i>
Viscous drag coefficient	<i>body(1).viscDrag.cd = [0 0 0 0 1.7 0];</i>
Viscous drag characteristic area [m ²]*	<i>body(1).viscDrag.characteristicArea = [0 0 0 0 1/4 * w * h^4 0];</i>
Initialize bodyClass for Base	<i>body(2) = bodyClass(h5_file);</i>
Geometry File	<i>body(2).geometryFile = 'geometry/cal_model - Concrete - 1_0cdg.stl';</i>
Creates Fixed Body	<i>body(2).mass = 'fixed';</i>

* Note that for the viscous drag characteristic area, *w = 17.7m* and *h = 10.6m* (see Figure 4.5)

⁶ Vuorinen, M. (2018) [1072] MEGAROLLER WP1 - WEC-Sim model: pre-validation and verification input. [E-mail] Message to: Laporte Weywada, P. 23/05/2018.

4.5.3.2 Constraint and PTO Classes

Constraint and PTO classes are similar implementations, with both blocks connecting the WEC bodies to on one another (and possibly to the seabed) by constraining DOFs. Additionally, the WEC-Sim PTO block includes the option of applying linear damping and spring loads.

The properties of the constraint class (constraintClass) are defined in the constraint object. Within the *wecSimInputFile.m*, users must initialize each iteration the constraint class (constraintClass) and specify the constraint name, by including the following lines:

```
constraint((#)) = constraintClass('constraint name');
```

For rotational constraints, the user also needs to specify the location of the rotational joint(s) with respect to the global reference frame in the *constraint((#)).loc* variable.

The PTO (ptoClass) extracts power from relative body motion with respect to a fixed reference frame or another body. The properties of the PTO class (ptoClass) are defined in the PTO object. Within the *wecSimInputFile.m*, users must initialise each in iteration the ptoClass and specify the PTO name, by including the following lines:

```
pto((#)) = ptoClass('pto name');
```

For rotational PTOs, the user also needs to specify the location of the rotational joint with respect to the global reference frame in the *pto((#)).loc* variable. A subroutine was created to read the tank test output data and save the measured PTO torque time-series in a variable loaded in the WEC-Sim model.

The values used for the key constraints and PTO properties are described in Table 4.8. Other constraints and PTO properties, default values, and functions can be found by typing *doc constraintClass* or *doc ptoClass*, respectively, in the MATLAB command window.

Table 4.8 Simulation properties defined in the Constraint and PTO Classes

Class	Property	Command and Value
Constraint	Initialize ConstraintClass for Constraint	<i>constraint(1) = constraintClass('Constraint1');</i>
	Constraint Location [m]	<i>constraint(1).loc = [0 0 -water_depth];</i>
PTO	Initialize ptoClass for PTO	<i>pto(1) = ptoClass('PTO1');</i>
	PTO Location [m]	<i>pto(1).loc = [0 0 zPTO];</i>
	PTO torque time-series	PTOexp_measured

4.6 Simulation Outputs

Once the setup of the WEC-Sim model is complete, the simulation may be initiated by entering “*wecSim*” in the MATLAB command window. After the pre-processing steps, the Mechanical Explorer window illustrates the model as the simulation progresses. When the simulation ends, the WEC-Sim post-processing generates a “*output*” structure variable, which contains all the model block time-series. The WEC-Sim WEC model output follows the format presented in Table 4.9.

Table 4.9 Key output parameters in the output structure WEC-Sim variable

Output fields	Subfields
wave	elevation
bodies	<i>motion</i> : position, velocity, acceleration <i>forces</i> : total, excitation, radiation damping, linear damping, added mass, restoring, morrison and viscous
ptos	<i>motion</i> : position, velocity, acceleration <i>force</i> : total, actuation, constraint, internal mechanics <i>power</i> : internal mechanics
constraints	<i>motion</i> : position, velocity, acceleration force constraint
ptosim	piston (compressible or non compressible fluid) checkValve valve accumulator hydraulicMotor rotaryGenerator pmLinearGenerator pmRotaryGenerator motionMechanism
mooring	<i>motion</i> : position, velocity force mooring
moorDyn (external files)	Lines Line# (for each line)

Following the development of the WEC model described in Section 4, a preliminary validation case study in presented in Section 5, comparing WEC-Sim outputs against the measurements from the tank tests conducted in the Queen’s University of Belfast.

5 PRELIMINARY VALIDATION EXERCISE

5.1 Background: Queen's University of Belfast Tank Tests

The case study presented in this section aims to act as a preliminary validation exercise, comparing the initial WEC-Sim outputs against measurements from tank tests conducted at the Queen's University of Belfast facility between August 2017 and January 2018 (see e.g. <http://aw-energy.com/news/awe-and-queens-university-belfast-finish-waveroller-tank-tests/>), using a previous design iteration of the WaveRoller WEC at 1:36 scale.

The testing campaign, which ended in January 2018, concentrated on recording the loads at multiple locations, mainly on the foundation and the flap, under a wide range of design conditions of varying tides, sea states and wave directions.

The tank tests were conducted within the MaRINET2 project funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 Framework Programme, under grant agreement no 731084.

The available tank test outputs include⁷:

- Flap measurements
 - Position
 - Surge force
 - Heave force
 - PTO torque
- Foundation measurements
 - 6DOF force and moments
- Free-surface elevation time-series
 - Measured in the absence of the WEC at its deployment location

From the above, the preliminary validation exercise reported in this section focused on a comparison of the time-series of PTO torque and flap motion in pitch. Prior to conducting the preliminary validation exercise, the analysis of the tank data identified a number key assumptions and limitations, including:

- Wave measurements
 - The wave gauge measuring the free-surface elevation at the location of the device may not have been deployed at the exact position, as the orientation of the WEC model was updated between calibration and deployment. To mitigate the uncertainty, it is noted that, when comparing the flap motion in pitch, the WEC-Sim time-series outputs were shifted to match the zero-crossing instants with the corresponding times in the experimental measurement signals.
 - Overall, it was seen that the free-surface elevation time-series feature a non-zero mean. Moreover, regular wave measurements showed some irregularities in the peaks and troughs, potentially showing tank limitations (e.g. with refraction effects). The time series

⁷ Vuorinen, M. (2018) [1072] MEGAROLLER WP1 - WEC-Sim model: pre-validation and verification input. [E-mail] Message to: Laporte Weywada, P. 01/08/2018.

of free-surface elevation measured in the tank were used as input in the WEC-Sim simulations.

- PTO torque
 - The PTO torque vs. pitch velocity profile measured in the tank showed significant variation with respect to the targeted Coulomb profile, in particular for large waves.
- Scale effects
 - The tank measurements were provided as full-scale equivalent values for comparison with WEC-Sim outputs. In CAT's experience, the understanding of the limitations (and of the associated uncertainty) of testing non-performance conditions at small scale is critical when selecting the model scale. In particular, issues such as a distortion of the ratio between inertial and viscous forces may arise at small scales [Cruz, 2008], and the extrapolation of the dominant effects using Froude scaling (that accounts for the ratio between inertial and gravitational forces) should in such cases be considered with caution.

Regarding the WEC-Sim simulations, it is noted that the current WEC-Sim implementation of the drag force does not take into account the relative velocity between the body and the fluid, but rather the absolute body velocity. In future steps, and as required, it is anticipated that the drag coefficient can be calibrated against experimental data, or that an implementation considering the relative velocity can be used.

In the following subsections, comparisons between tank measurements and WEC-Sim outputs are presented for a regular wave case (Section 5.2) and for an irregular wave case (Section 5.3). The regular wave case analysis is extended in Section 5.4 by considering nonlinear hydrodynamics, presenting also some initial illustrative results from the structural dynamics module (considering a flexible prime mover).

5.2 Regular Wave Case

This subsection describes the preliminary comparison of the WEC-Sim model outputs with experimental data in regular waves using measurements from the tank tests at Queen's University of Belfast conducted between August 2017 and January 2018. The multi-body WEC model for the system is the same as that shown in Figure 4.11, using the WEC inputs described in Section 4.5.3. The target input wave condition was a regular wave with 2m wave height and 10s wave period, in a water depth of 14.5m (all full-scale equivalent). For validation purposes, the environmental input conditions were defined in the input file as the exact measured time series of free-surface elevation, using the following commands:

```
waves = waveClass('etaImport');  
waves.etaDataFile = 'wave_elev_exp.mat';
```

where *wave_elev_exp.mat* is a MATLAB file that describes the wave elevation time series as measured in the tank. Figure 5.1 shows an extract of the wave elevation time series as measured in the tank.

Figure 5.1 Extract of wave elevation time series measured in the tank – Test 055A (target wave: $H=2\text{m}$, $T=10\text{s}$)

Figure 5.2 illustrates the PTO torque as a function of angular velocity in pitch. As already mentioned in Section 3.4, the experimental measurements evidenced significant variations in PTO torque as a function of the absolute angular velocity. Figure 5.2 also displays in red the PTO torque profile input in the PTO block of the WEC-Sim model as a look-up-table.

Figure 5.2 PTO torque profile: torque value against flap angular velocity in pitch – as measured in the tank (blue) and as input in the WEC-Sim PTO model look-up-table (red) – Test 055A

Figure 5.3 shows the time series of flap motion and PTO torque extracted from the simulation output and experimental measurements. Figure 5.4 illustrates the agreement in angular pitch motion of the flap output by the WEC-Sim simulation and measured in the tank, along with a linear fit of the scatter diagram (blag line). The under-estimation of the amplitude of motion by WEC-Sim is likely to be related to an under estimation of the drag force – in particular, the current WEC-Sim implementation of the drag force

does not take into account the relative velocity between the body and the fluid, but rather the absolute body velocity (see Section 5.1).

Figure 5.3 Comparison of time-series of motion in pitch (left) and PTO torque (right) between tank measurement (red) and WEC-Sim estimates (blue) – 150s extract – Test 055A

Figure 5.4 Scatter diagram of motion in pitch as measured in the tank (horizontal axis) and estimated in WEC-Sim (vertical axis) – Test 055A

5.3 Irregular Wave Case

This subsection describes the preliminary comparison of the WEC-Sim model outputs with experimental data in irregular waves, with 3.5m wave height and 10s wave period, in a water depth of 14.5m (full-scale equivalent). Figure 5.5 shows an extract of the wave elevation time series as measured in the tank.

Figure 5.5 Extract of wave elevation time series measured in the tank – Test 049A (target sea state: Hs=3.5m, T=10s, JONSWAP spectrum)

Similar to the regular case (see Section 5.2), the wave input condition was defined in the input file as following:

```
waves = waveClass('etaImport');
waves.etaDataFile = 'wave_elev_exp.mat';
```

where *wave_elev_exp.mat* is the matlab file that describes the wave elevation time series as measured in the tank. The measured signals of wave elevation were also triggered to align the up-crossing zeros in the PTO torque signals as measured in the tank and output by WEC-Sim.

The target maximum PTO torque for the case considered is shown in Figure 3.4. Figure 5.6 also displays simultaneous measurements of PTO torque and flap angular velocity in pitch, with the addition of the PTO torque profile input in the PTO block of the WEC-Sim model as a look-up-table. The range of PTO torque observed in the tank reaches instantaneous values substantially larger than the target, with values reaching up to 250% the target value.

Figure 5.6 PTO torque profile: torque value against flap angular velocity in pitch – as measured in the tank (blue) and as input in the WEC-Sim PTO model look-up-table (red) – Test 049A

Figure 5.7 shows the time series of flap motion and PTO torque extracted from the simulation output and experimental measurements. Overall, the motion signal output by WEC-Sim matches reasonably well the tank measurements, despite the discrepancies in the PTO torque imposed.

Figure 5.7 Comparison of time-series of motion in pitch (left) and PTO torque (right) between tank measurement (red) and WEC-Sim estimates (blue) – 150s extract – Test 049A

Figure 5.8 Scatter diagram of motion in pitch as measured in the tank (horizontal axis) and estimated in WEC-Sim (vertical axis) – Test 049A

Figure 5.8 illustrates the agreement in angular pitch motion of the flap output by the WEC-Sim simulation and measured in the tank. The black line corresponds to a linear regression fit of the scatter diagram. Considering the uncertainties associated with the models, in particular regarding the PTO torque profile and the approximation in the drag force implementation (see also Section 5.1), the agreement in the pitch motion of the flap as estimated in WEC-Sim and output in the tank is relatively good, with WEC-Sim overall under-estimating the tank results by about 25%.

5.4 Regular Case with Nonlinear Hydrodynamics

In this subsection, the same regular wave case as in Section 5.2 was considered, adding the consideration of nonlinear hydrodynamic forces in the simulation. For that purpose, the nonlinear key word *simu.nlHydro* was activated (*simu.nlHydro* = 1).

It is noted that when using nonlinear Froude-Krylov and buoyancy forces option, the wave input is limited to standard shaped waves, i.e. regular waves of standard shaped spectrum. For this reason, the measured surface elevation time series cannot be used, and the target regular wave of 2.0m wave height and 10s wave period was used instead.

The environment input condition was defined in the input file as following:

```
waves = waveClass('regular');
waves.H = 2.0;
waves.T = 10;
```

Similar to the regular case presented in Section 5.2, the PTO torque profile shown in Figure 5.2 was input in the PTO block of the WEC-Sim model in the form of a look-up-table.

Figure 5.9 shows the time series of flap motion and PTO torque extracted from the simulation output. In Figure 5.10, the nonlinear hydrodynamic pressure distribution over the wetted surface of the flap is displayed (at instant t=1000s). As described in Section 3.3.2, it is envisaged that such output, along with the force time series, are used as input to the structural flexible module.

Figure 5.9 Extract of WEC-Sim time-series of motion in pitch (left) and PTO torque (right) – Test 055A with target wave input

Figure 5.10 Nonlinear hydrodynamic pressures on the flap at instant t=1000s – Test 055A

As an initial test, a static structural model of WEC was built using the CALFEM open-source MATLAB FE solver [Austrell, 2004]. The model consists of a number of cylindrical beams arranged to cover the entire width and height of the flap as illustrated Figure 5.11. For this initial test, the structural model was a 2D representation of the structure. The beams were given arbitrary properties (steel material, diameter of 0.3m) for the initial test but can be later be calibrated to more accurately represent other structural materials. The model was run as a stand-alone post-processor (i.e. the method illustrated in Figure 3.2, taking the force and pressure time-series output by WEC-Sim as inputs.

Figure 5.11 Illustration of the 2D structural model setup

Figure 5.12 shows the total surge force (FX) distributed onto the flap at an example time of t=400s. It should be noted that the forces are only applied at the nodes, with MATLAB linearly interpolating between points to create a surface.

Figure 5.12 Surge force (FX) applied to the structural model at t=400s

It should be noted that this initial structural model was created for illustrative purposes only, and is not intended to represent the stiffness of a MegaRoller WEC flap. Further work will be conducted to develop the structural dynamics module and test the methods detailed in Section 4.

Following the implementation of the baseline WEC-Sim model presented in this report, Section 6 introduces the immediate next steps currently envisaged in order to enable a detailed assessment of the distributed loads affecting the MegaRoller WEC system.

6 NEXT STEPS

In this document, the fundamental theory associated with the MegaRoller WEC-Sim model and the essential aspects related to its practical use were described. A preliminary validation exercise was also reported, using results related to a previous design iteration of the WaveRoller WEC tested at Queen's University of Belfast. The resulting deliverable represents the main output of Task 1.2, which aimed to define and develop a nonlinear model of the MegaRoller WEC.

The primary objective of the model is to enable a detailed assessment of the distributed loads affecting the MegaRoller WEC system, in an effort to support the design process in WP2. In particular, the model will be used to assess the influence of the distributed loading contributions over the WEC prime mover, i.e. the flap, accounting for the coupled nature of interaction(s) between the flap and the power take-off (PTO) load sources.

Following the implementation of the initial MegaRoller WEC-Sim model, the following immediate next steps are anticipated:

- In Task 1.3, detailed survivability and reliability metrics (e.g. survival functions) will be estimated for a range of design situations, focusing on Ultimate Limit State (ULS) and/or Fatigue Limit State (FLS) conditions. Following the identification of a critical set of design load cases (DLCs), the load characterisation will be conducted numerically using the WEC-Sim model, updated to include inputs specific to the MegaRoller WEC device. Further developments such as the addition of slap and slam forces, the implementation of spread waves or the conceptualisation of a novel structural dynamics module are envisaged. The load characterisation exercise will be documented in [D1.2, 2019].

It is noted that the test bench upgrade design conducted in Tasks 1.5 and 2.3 will rely on the results of Task 1.3 to inform the loads and expected hinge motions that the drivetrain will face.

- In Task 1.4, additional verification, pre-validation and validation activities of the WEC-Sim model will be conducted. For example, the verification of the numerical model will consist in a code-to-code comparison against state-of-the-art tools. The pre-validation exercise initiated in the context of the present deliverable may also be extended using further tank measurements. Finally, and deepening on its applicability, data from Task 5.2 may also inform additional validation steps. The verification, pre-validation and validation exercise will be documented in [D1.7, 2021].

It is noted that the validation methodology and plan will be defined in the context of Task 5.1, documented in [D5.1, 2020].

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